

UZBEKISTAN-KOREA: CURRENT AND PROSPECTS OF
MUTUAL COOPERATION

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

O‘ZBEKISTONDA KOREYA AVTOMOBIL SANOATIGA 30 YIL

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Аннотация: Koreya avtomobil sanoati jahon bozoriga qanday kirib keldi va uning O‘zbekiston avtomobil sanoatidagi o‘rni qanday? Bu ikki davlat o‘rtasidagi barcha kelishuvlar va kelajakda mo‘ljallangan yangi loyihalar quyida keltirilib, elektromobillar haqida subyektiv fikrlar bildirilgan.

Калит so‘zlar: Sanoat, elektr, ishlab chiqarish, xizmat ko‘rsatish, bozor.

**30 ЛЕТ КОРЕЙСКОЙ АВТОМОБИЛЬНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ
В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ**

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Аннотация: Как корейский автопром вышел на мировой рынок и какова его роль в автомобилестроении Узбекистана? Ниже представлены все договоренности между этими двумя странами и новые проекты на будущее, а также приведены субъективные мнения об электромобилях.

Ключевые слова: Промышленность, электроэнергетика, производство, сервис, рынок.

**30 YEARS OF THE KOREAN AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRY IN
UZBEKISTAN**

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Annotation: How the Korean automobile industry entered the world market and what its role in the Uzbek automobile industry? All agreements between these two countries and new projects for the future are mentioned below and subjective opinions are expressed about electro cars.

Key points: Industry, electric, production, service, market.

It is not a secret to anyone that South Korea’s automobile industry was claimed to have been the fourth largest car producing country in the world in 2021. And having remained as much as one of the most important sectors, automotive industry has reached to over 10% to the nation’s total GDP, which contributed to the economic growth, on 16 September, 2021. In fact, the Korean automotive industry has developed in 4 stages:

- In 1962-1973, cars were assembled from imported components;
- In 1974, South Korea's automobile industry has begun to develop gradually;
- In 1983, the Republic of Korea launched the export and mass production of cars;
- In 1998, the period of the last stage, which can be called a globalization period.

The first car in South Korea was made in a workshop on the outskirts of Seoul from the scraps of American cars. Later, the assembly of cars from spare parts of American and Italian companies was started. Cars were made from Chevrolet components and spare parts. However, their quality was not good and their number could not be enough for the demand of the population. In 1962, the government announced its program for the development of the automobile industry and passed a law to protect this industry. In this year, 1962, 3 companies were founded:

1. KyungSung Precision Industry (later Kia Industry) started assembling cars in cooperation with Mazda in 1964;
2. Ha Dong-Hwan Automobile Industry Co. (now SsangYong Motor Company);

3. Saenara Automobile and Nissan Motor Co. was organized with technical support.

In general, between 1962 and 1968, the leading companies of the Korean automobile industry were founded. In 1965, Asia Motors Company and in 1968, Hyundai Motor Company started working with the technical support of Ford Motor Company. It is worth noting that at first all these companies were engaged only in car assembly.

1-pic. Second generation Hyundai Pony liftback (EU spec)

After some time, a joint venture between Daewoo Holding and General Motors was opened on the basis of Shinju and became Daewoo Motors and Asia Motors joined Kia. Each of them had to fulfill the task of reaching the level of development of cars from 50,000 units per year and increasing the volume of local components in exchange for political support and preferential loans. Hyundai, a representative of the Korean auto industry, managed to deliver a cheap, but high-quality car for the US market. The subsequent success of Korean automakers can be easily attributed to public demand. They built their internal policies on this basis. Meanwhile, from the 1970s to the 1997 Asian crisis, the Korean automobile industry was divided between three major companies: Kia Motors, Daewoo Motors and Hyundai Motors. The political situation of 1988 also affected to the automobile giants. As a result, opening joint ventures in foreign countries became the demand of that time. These enterprises were opened mainly in developing countries such as Romania, Ukraine, Poland, Russia and Uzbekistan. The first stage of car production began in 1992 with a profitable contract with South Korea's Daewoo Motors company, 50% to 50% share contract, was signed between “Avtoqishxo’jmashⁱ” of Uzbekistan and Daewoo and this contract made a huge turn in the automotive industry. In 1993, the UzDaewoo Auto company was registered with the state and construction works began in the city of Asaka, Andijan region. And its total amount was 658 million dollars. At that time, the car manufacturing plant was equipped with the most modern technologies of Korea, qualified workers were accepted, including about

1,000 young people from Uzbekistan who went to Korea to study. The production of the first car at the plant began in 1996. And the first Damas car was produced in March, then Tico and Nexia cars in June. On July 19, 1996, the opening ceremony of the Plant was held and the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, took part in it. And he said at the solemn ceremony: “Our country, as well as our far and near neighbors, understand well that to build such a huge factory, not only economic and financial capabilities, but also a big heart must also have”.

In this way, the automobile industry was launched between Uzbekistan and South Korea, and several dozen models of cars are on sale today.

2-pic.
Chevrolet Lacetti
(2005-2010)

The government plans to transfer the

company “Uzavtosanoat” to the production of electric cars only. In addition, fees for the purchase of electric cars within the country and their temporary import have been cancelled.

This resolution was mentioned in the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated December 29 (VMQ-812). In addition, the fee for the purchase and (or) temporary importation of electric vehicles within the country (paid when registering the vehicle at the Ministry of Internal Affairs) has been canceled.

In the eyes of the world community, all modern technologies are becoming more advanced. In particular, in the field of auto transport, great achievements and constant changes have become commonplace. After all, since the 19th century, the term “car” has been used closely with the term “fuel”. Today’s generation of technology is on the verge of ending it completely.

This is how gasoline engines end their life. The appearance of electric cars on the roads in the near future will not be a secret to anyone. Their number is increasing in foreign countries. Major car manufacturing companies also had time to demonstrate their electric cars.

An electric car is a car that moves with the help of one or more electric motors with a battery. The increase in the amount of toxic gases emitted by internal combustion engine cars served as one of the main factors for the rapid development of electric cars. One charge of batteries in an electric car (energy

reserve) is enough to travel up to 100 km. Electric cars are designed for driving in the city: the walking part, the body is lightened with a separate transmission and the batteries are designed to be easy to replace. The use of electric cars reduces noise and air pollution in cities. Electric cars are produced in the USA, China, Korea, Japan, Germany and several other developed countries of the world and their single charge is enough to travel up to 200 km.

3-pic. Kona electric – ECO | Hyundai Malaysia

The Hyundai company, which has its place in the automobile industry and is among the Top 10 companies, has seriously entered the race of modern electric cars and has been showing its results one after another. Of course, the most popular and successful ones can be distinguished among them: Hyundai Ioniq and Hyundai Kona. Both of these are distinguished in the world of electric cars by their convenience and affordability.

Hyundai Ioniq – produced since 2017. Mainly for walking around the city-designed car. Hyundai Ioniq can be controlled in 3 different ways while driving: Drive mood – Eco, Eco+, Sport mood. The battery can cover a distance of 311 km with a full charge (weather affects during non-conductive time). 8-year battery warranty (or up to 160,000,000 km). It can reach 100 km/h in 9.7 seconds. This model includes GPS Navigator, front and rear surveillance cameras and all the other advantages.

4-pic. Hyundai Kona – produced since 2017.

Like Hyundai Ioniq, it has 3 modes of control: Drive mood – Eco, Eco+, Sport mood. It can reach a distance of 420-400 km with a single full charge. All

equipment is automated (comfort). One of its distinguishing features is the smart button (it will automatically monitor you when driving in one lane. As soon as the driver loses his vigilance, the program will start and control will be established). It has a large monitor for multiplayer, calling and other services. GPS navigator, communication system and all similar services are implemented through this monitor.

During the visit of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Listem-Fergana joint venture in the city of Fergana, a presentation of notable projects planned to be implemented in the

region was held. According to the press service of the President, Hyundai and Hyundai have discussed projects for the production of electric cars in the Kukan free economic zone.

The President approved the projects and emphasized the need to pay special attention to quality and time in their implementation. Hyundai Ioniq hatchback and Hyundai Kona crossovers were shown in the project. According to the planned project, the production of modern electric cars and the creation of infrastructure for them will be carried out in cooperation with Hyundai Motor and Evergreen Motors of South Korea and the Ministry of Investments and Foreign Trade of Uzbekistan. According to the project, it was planned to start the construction of the plant in 2021, and to start mass production of electric cars in Uzbekistan in 2023.

Summary

From the above information and comments, it can be concluded that the automobile industry of Uzbekistan and South Korea has gone through a long period together. Korean cars shaped the image of the Uzbek auto industry. And of course, Hyundai Ioniq and Hyundai Kona cars can be an alternative choice for the territory and residents of Uzbekistan. These state-of-the-art vehicles, capable of driving in the inner city and in all weather conditions, with seats for 5 people, do not need any type of fuel and are significantly more economical and affordable than their competitors. It will give a new impetus to the automotive industry.

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¹State concern (Avtomobil qishloq xo‘jalik mashinalari)